

Development and Standardization of Herbal Mix for Hot Beverages

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 16 ,2025</p> <p>Accepted: October 19,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Herbal,Mix, Hot Beverages, Tulsi, Turmeric</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17392333</p>	<p><i>Herbal mix is essentially an herbal mixture made from leaves, seeds or roots of various plants.It gives a strong medicinal benefit such as anti inflammatory, anti oxidant and anti bacterial properties.Tulsi isan herb used in Ayurveda and in some herbal products. The tulsi plant has many medicinal properties. The tulsi leaves are a nerve tonic and also sharpen memory. Tulsi leaves has strengthening effect on the kidney, has a beneficial effect in cardiac disease and the weakness resulting from them. It reduces the level of blood cholesterol. Chewing tulsi leaves relieves cold and flu.Turmeric is the traditional yellow colour root belonging to the family of ginger. Commonly used as herb and spice worldwide, its properties make it smell poignant and strong in flavour which is a little bitter in tasteThe methodology of the studywas to develop the Tulsi herbal mix and Turmeric herbal mix. The study result revealed that variant V₁ and V₂ of tulsi herbal mix werehighly acceptable. Similarly, in turmeric herbal mix the acceptability for V₂ and V₃ was seems to be higher .</i></p>

Introduction

A modern lifestyle of many Indian people today, especially living in big cities, needs fast paced and practical things almost in all aspects, including preparation, processing and presentation of food. It creates a society who loves instant food products such as food that are ready to cook and ready to eat. One of the potential products that can be developed into an instant food is herbal mix. For fulfilling consumer social requirements dried herbal mix play a vital role in it. Herbal mix can become good food, as it is easily prepared and taking only short time to serve. (Krejov et al 2007).

Hot and sweet beverage native to the Sundanese people of West Java, Indonesia. The main ingredients are coconut milk and Aren palm sugar; usually to add taste, a small amount of ginger and a small pinch of salt For example tea , coffee, lemon water etc.(Zeegers et al 2001).

India produces a wide variety of spices including cardamoms, chillies, black pepper, mustard, coriander. Indian cuisine is also known for its rich taste which it derives from numerous spices.

- The demand of Indian spices is high in the global market due to their rich aroma, texture, and taste. India has the largest domestic market for spices in the world. The primary spices imported from India are pepper, chilli, turmeric, coriander, cumin, and fennel.
- Spices are generally used as important food adjuncts help to avoid monotony, disguise unpleasant odours, Aid digestion, Increase rate of perspiration, resulting in lowering body temperature, carminative and antiseptic, antioxidants, anti-inflammatory, perfumes, soaps, incenses, dyes etc.(Dubey, 2010).

TURMERIC-

Turmeric is likely best known as a pungent and bright yellow spice in Indian cuisine. It's a tropical plant, and can only be grown outdoors (Leong –Skornicker, et al (2008). Health benefit- It helps deal with skin problems. Turmeric powder can be used for healing cuts and wounds .It makes copying with diabetes easier (Tayem et al 2006).

BLACK PEPPER-

Black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) is a flowering vine in the family Piperaceae, cultivated for its fruit, known as a peppercorn which is usually dried and used as a spice and seasoning. When fresh and fully mature, the fruit is about 5 mm (0.20 in) in diameter, dark red, and contains a single seed, like all drupes (Paul 2016).Health benefits- It helps coping with cold, cough, infections etc. It helps to deal with muscles pain and digestive problem . It is also beneficial remedy for chest pains, fever etc . (chaleb et al 2007).

CLOVES-

The clove tree is an evergreen that grows up to 8–12 metres (26–39 ft) tall, with large leaves and crimsoms flowers grouped in terminal clusters. The flower buds initially have a pale hue, gradually turn green, then transition to a bright red when ready for harvest. Cloves are harvested at 1.5–2 centimetres (0.59–0.79 in) long, and consist of a long calyx that terminates in four spreading sepals, and four unopened petals that form a small central ball (Merr & Perry 2011).Health benefits-Cloves is helpful in tooth ache problem and score gum (Chauhan 2017).

GINGER-

It is a flowering plant whose rhizome, ginger, is widely used as a spice and a folk medicine. It is a herbaceous perennial which grows annual pseudostems (false stems made of the rolled bases of leaves) about one meter tall bearing narrow leaf blades. The inflorescence bears flowers having pale yellow petals with purple edges, and arise directly from the rhizome on separate (Wonjung 2018). Health benefits- Helps to avoid digestive problems. It is beneficial for coping with cough and cold.(Dubey2017).

Materials And Methods

Procurement-

The raw materials were procured from the local market (Jaipur, Rajasthan) for processing and development of the product. This includes turmeric powder, tulsi powder, black pepper powder, cloves, cinnamon powder, cardamom powder, dry ginger powder.

Formulation of Tulsi herbal mix

Boil 150 ml of water. Mix all the dry ingredients (tulsi powder, black pepper powder, cloves, cinnamon powder, cardamom powder, dry ginger powder) in it. Boil all the ingredients till the volume was almost half (75 ml). For the herbal mix.

Table no 1. Tulsi herbal mix composition table

Ingredients	0.5% incorporating	1% incorporating	2% incorporating	Control
Tulsi leaves	0.5g	1g	2g	-
Ginger powder	2g	2g	2g	2g
Black pepper	.75g	.75g	.75g	.75g
Cardamom powder	1g	1g	1g	1g
Cinnamon powder	1g	1g	1g	1g

Drying process

Tulsi leaves kept for shadow drying for 2 days. Then leaves were grinded for the powder formation.

Product Development

Tulsi Herbal Mix

Boil 150ml of water. Mix all the dry ingredients (tulsi powder, black pepper powder, cloves, cinnamon powder, cardamom powder, dry ginger powder) in it. Boil all the ingredients till the volume was almost half (75 ml). For the herbal mix.

Turmeric Herbal Mix -

Mix all the dry ingredients (turmeric powder, black pepper powder, cloves, cinnamon powder, elachi powder, dry ginger powder) together and add in 150 ml of water. Boil them until it became 75 ml in volume.

Table no.2 Turmeric herbal mix composition table

Ingredients	1% incorporating	1.5% incorporating	2% incorporating	Control
Turmeric powder	1g	1.5g	2g	-
Black pepper	0.2g	0.2g	0.2g	0.2g
Cardamom powder	0.5g	0.5g	0.5g	0.5g
Cinnamon powder	0.5g	0.5g	0.5g	0.5g
Ginger powder	1g	1g	1g	1g

Formulation of turmeric herbal mix-

Mix all the dry ingredients (turmeric powder, black pepper powder, cloves, cinnamon powder, elachi powder, dry ginger powder) together and add in 150 ml of water. Boil them until it became 75 ml in volume.

Proximate nutrient content-

Energy, protein, fat, carbohydrate content of the developed products were calculated with the help of Indian Food Composition Table (IFCT, 2017).

Sensory Evaluation-

The samples were subjected to sensory evaluation on 9-point hedonic scale. There were 5 attributes like colour, taste, appearance, texture, overall acceptability.(Mishra 2019). The scores represented the following: 1-dislike extremely, 2-dislike very much, 3-dislike moderately, 4-dislike slightly, 5-neither like nor dislike, 6-like slightly, 7-like moderately, 8-like very much and 9-like extremely.(Ranganna, 1996).

MOISTURE CONTENT -

Method-Weigh two grams of sample in aluminium dishes using a mettle balance and placed in a hot air oven maintained at 130°C for 1 hr. It was then cooled to room temperature in the desiccators. Loss in weight in percentage was reported as % moisture content, which is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Moisture (g/100g \%)} = \frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{weight of the sample}} \times 100$$

Result and Discussion

Sensory Evaluation for Tulsi Herbal Mix-

The sensory score was shown in Table 4.1 the colour of tulsi herbal mix changes from yellow to light yellow after boiling. Variant V3 (7.00±1.09) is maximum in mean score for colour attribute and minimum in Variant V1 (6.04±1.02). The taste for tulsi herbal mix is maximum in Variant V3 (7.02±0.74) and minimum in control (6.04±1.02). The appearance for tulsi herbal mix is maximum in Variant V2 (6.08±1.16) and minimum in control (6.04±0.08). The texture for tulsi herbal mix is maximum in variant V1 (6.00±0.92) and minimum in control (6.02±0.12). The odour for tulsi herbal mix is maximum in variant V3 (7.04±1.35) and minimum in Variant V1 (7.00±0.63). The overall acceptability was maximum in variant V2 (7.00±1.09) and minimum in control (6.04±0.08). Variant 3 is highly acceptable as compared to control and other variants.

Table 4.1 Mean Sensory Evaluation of Tulsi Herbal Mix

Parameter	Control	V1	V2	V3
Colour	6.06±1.02	6.06±0.49	7.00±1.09	7.00±1.09
Taste	6.04±1.02	6.06±0.49	6.08±0.98	7.02±0.74
Appearance	6.04±0.08	6.06±0.47	6.08±0.98	6.08±1.16
Texture	6.04±0.08	6.06±0.34	6.02±0.78	6.06±0.08
Odour	7.02±0.78	7.00±0.63	6.08±0.98	7.04±1.35
Overall	6.04±0.08	6.06±0.49	7.00±1.09	6.08±0.98

Data are reported as Mean ±SD

4.1.2 Sensory evaluation for Turmeric Herbal Mix

Sensory evaluation score for Turmeric Herbal Mix was shown in the Table 4.2. The colour of turmeric herbal mix change from green to light brown after boiling is maximum in variant V3 (6.08±0.74) and minimum in control (6.08±0.42). The taste of turmeric herbal mix is maximum in variant V3 (7.00±0.82) and minimum in control (6.02±0.42). The appearance of turmeric herbal mix was liquid was maximum in variant V3(7.00±0.82)and minimum in control (6.08±0.02).The texture of turmeric herbal mix was maximum in Variant2 (6.02±0.46) and minimum in control (6.02±0.22).The odour for turmeric herbal mix was maximum in Variant V3(7.00±0.32) and minimum in control(6.02±0.22).The overall acceptability was maximum in variant V3 (7.00±0.63) and minimum in Variant V3 (6.04±1.02).

Table 4.2 Mean Sensory Evaluation for Turmeric Herbal Mix

Attribute	Control	Variant 1	Variant2	Variant 3
Colour	6.08±0.42	6.08±0.74	6.08±0.74	6.04±0.08
Taste	6.04±0.49	7.00±0.63	6.04±0.08	6.02±1.16
Appearance	6.04±0.49	6.06±1.02	6.04±0.08	6.02±0.98
Texture	6.04±0.49	6.08±0.74	6.08±0.74	6.04±1.02
Odour	6.04±0.08	7.00±0.63	7.00±0.63	6.04±1.02
Overall acceptability	6.08±0.04	7.00±0.63	7.00±0.63	6.04±1.02

Data are reported as Mean ±SD

Table 3 Proximate content of tulsi herbal mix

Nutrients	Control	Variant1	Variant2	Variant3
Protein(g)	0.004	0.015	0.031	0.063
Energy(kcal)	0.09	0.15	0.23	0.46
Fat(g)	0.017	0.032	0.652	0.0128
Carbohydrate(g)	0.179	0.132	0.652	0.053

Proximate nutrient content of tulsi herbal mix shown in Table 4. Protein content of herbal mix ranges from 0.00g-0.063g. Protein content was found to be maximum in V₃. Energy content of herbal mix ranges from 0.09kcal-0.46kcal. Energy content of V₃ was found to be maximum. Fat content of herbal mix ranges from 0.0128g- 0.652g. Fat content was found maximum in V₂. Carbohydrate content of herbal mix ranges from 0.179g-0.053g. Carbohydrate content was found to be maximum in V₂.

Table 5 proximate content of turmeric herbal Mix

Nutrients	Control	Variant1	Variant2	Variant3
protein(g)	0.02	0.015	0.20	0.025
Energy(kcal)	2.30	2.35	2.43	2.99
Fat(g)	0.85	0.75	0.65	0.56
Carbohydrate(g)	0.0897	0.0984	0.0789	0.0678

Proximate nutrient content of turmeric herbal mix shown in Table 4. Protein content of herbal mix ranges from 0.015g-0.025g. Protein content was maximum in V₃. Energy content of herbal mix ranges from 2.30kcal-2.98kcal. Energy was maximum in V₃. Fat content of herbal mix ranges from 0.85g-0.56g. Fat content was maximum in V₁. Carbohydrate content in herbal mix ranges from 0.897g-0.0678g. Carbohydrate was maximum in V₃.

Conclusion

Tulsi leaves are rich in vitamins A, C, and K and minerals like calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, iron, and potassium. It also has a good amount of protein and fibre. Turmeric contains high content of potassium, niacin and other nutrients. Turmeric is a popular ingredient in many Indian, Caribbean and Asian dishes and has many nutritional benefits. Magnesium and iron are its most prominent nutrients, and many people can use it as spice. Turmeric is rich in magnesium. Tulsi and herbal mix are beneficial for human health.

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